

ANTECEDENTS OF ONLINE SHOPPING BEHAVIOUR WITH REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE CITY

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Abstract:

The e-Commerce sector has seen unprecedented growth in 2014. The growth was driven by rapid technology adoption led by the increasing use of devices such as smartphones and tablets, and access to the internet through broadband, 3G, etc, which led to an increased online consumer base. Furthermore, favoured demographics and a growing internet user base helped aid this growth. In terms of highlights, the growth shown by home grown players such as Flipkart and Snap deal and the huge investor interest around these companies displayed the immense potential of the market. The conclusion is that based on the customers perception towards service provided by the companies Flipkart has the highest priority to the service provided and the priority can be given by the customers to purchase their products in this website.

Key Words: Online Shopping, Customer & Flipkart

Introduction:

The online shopping involves buying and selling of goods and services through online. Online shopping means buying and selling of the goods and services online; internet is the best source to use this tool. Today the amount of trade that is conducted electronically using online shopping has increased with a wide spread usage of internet and technology. Online shopping includes transferring of funds online, marketing over internet, buying and selling of goods and services etc. The online shopping has become more popular among the customers. For online shopping the customers should have knowledge about usage of internet and computer. Internet has become the centre of not only our personal and social lives, but also our business and professional lives. The invention of the internet has created a new pattern of the traditional way people shop. Customers are no longer tied to the opening hours or specific locations; it may become active virtually at any time and any place to purchase products and services. The Internet is relatively new medium for the communication and the exchange of information which has become present in our daily lives. The number of Internet users is constantly increasing, which is also significance that online purchasing is increasing rapidly.

Statement of the Problem:

There is lack of proper clarity in the Government FDI policy and this has delayed the entry of the retail giants like Wal-Mart, Ikea, Tesco in India. As a result the existing domestic retail players in the country are only competing with each other. This retail competition has taken a whole new shape for the last few years. The new competition is about capturing the online retail space in the country as much as possible. This is because the increasing dependency on computers of the Indian middle class segment has given an opportunity for online retailing business in India to become popular. Internet has transformed the retail experience for consumers by activating their emotions and sparking the desire to buy through imagery, videos, virtual tryons, real-time feedback, free home delivery and getting the ownership of goods in discounted price. It is evident that this newest trend in the buying pattern of the consumers are opening new ways for the retail companies to sell their product through internet, but at the same time it is becoming a serious threat to the conventional model of selling products through physical shops.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the consumer's expectation towards online shopping.
- To study the reasons for the problems..
- To study about the customer's opinion towards the problems in online shopping.

Scope of the Study:

The study is to know about customers delay or hesitate to make decision for shopping online. and to determine the reasons and suggestions for the problems faced by the customers. India has witnessed a major breakthrough E-commerce success stories particularly in e-retail in Consumer Electronics & Fashion Apparel & Home Furnishing segments. E-commerce creates new opportunities for entrepreneurial start-ups. Ease of Internet access, Safe and secure payment modes coupled with aggressive marketing by E-Commerce Giants has

revolutionized this segment. Rapid development in mobile technology has given way to Mobile Commerce with many E-Commerce companies shifting to App only model. The main scope of the study is that it will be helpful for the companies to maintain their quality of service based on customers in future period of time.

Research Methodology:

Research Design: Research design is the detailed plan of conducting a research study. Descriptive research design has been used in the study.

Sample Area: The data has been collected from Coimbatore city as it has a high residential density with people from all over Tamil Nadu due to the high migration influx in recent years. The population is quite heterogeneous, with various dimensions such as religion, caste, customs, traditions, social hierarchy, language, literacy, education, occupation, income etc.

Sample Technique: Sampling technique is the choice of a subset of people from among a huge population to estimate characteristics of the 270 respondents. The simple random technique has been chosen for this study.

Simple Random Sampling: Simple random sampling method, assumes that each and every unit in the population has equal chance of occurrence or equal probability of occurrence and the sampling units are selected randomly. An unbiased random selection of individuals is important to represent the population. The researchers have taken 270 samples randomly from the total population. Primary sources of data collected through questionnaire & secondary source from magazines, journals and website.

Structure of the Instrument: For collecting primary data, structured questionnaire has been used. It is the most popular method used when the population and sample size are large. It was designed to cater to all areas and aspects of the study.

Tools and Techniques Used for Analysis: Simple percentage analysis, Chi-square test and Weighted average method

Limitations of the Study: The study has got certain limitation of which a few are listed below:

- The results and findings are confined to a limited area.
- The opinions of the respondents may be biased.
- Time and resource constraint.
- Since the data was collected using questionnaire, there is a possibility of ambiguous replies or omission of replies altogether to certain items mentioned in the questionnaire.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Demo-Graphic Variables	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage
Gender	Male	190	70.4
	Female	80	29.6
	Total	270	100
Marital Status	Married	55	20.4
	Unmarried	215	79.6
	Total	270	100
Place of the Respondents	Rural	217	80.4
	Urban	53	19.6
	Total	270	100
Age of the Respondents	Up to 20 years	65	24.1
	20-40 years	95	35.2
	40-60 years	84	31.1
	Above 60 years	26	9.6
	Total	270	100
Educational Qualification	Schooling	7	2.6
	Diploma	7	2.6
	Under graduate	145	53.7
	Post graduate	88	32.6
	Professional degree	23	8.5
	Total	270	100
Occupation	Student	70	25.9
	Private job	86	31.9
	Government job	32	11.9
	Home maker	26	9.6
	Business	56	20.7
	Total	270	100

Interpretation:

From the above table it is clear that out of 270 respondents, 70.4% are male and 29.6% are female. 20.4% were married and 79.6% were unmarried. 80.4% of the respondents were from rural area and the rest 19.6% of the respondents from urban area. 35.2% of the respondents aged between 20-40 years, 31.1% of the respondents aged between 40-60 years, 24.1% of the respondents aged up to 20 years and the remaining 9.6% of the respondents aged above 60 years. 53.7% of the respondents were completed their under graduation, 32.6% of the respondents were completed their post-graduation, 8.5% of the respondents were completed their professional degree, 2.6% of the respondents were completed their schooling and the remaining 2.6% of the respondents were completed their diploma. 31.9% of the respondents were going for private job, 25.9% of the respondents were students, 20.7% of the respondents were doing business, 11.9% of the respondents were going for government job and the rest 9.6% of the respondents were homemakers. 36.3% of the respondents were earning more than Rs.60,000, 31.5% of the respondents were earning from Rs.40,001-Rs.60,000, 28.1% of the respondents were earning from Rs.20,000-Rs. 40,000 and the rest 4.1% of the respondents were earning less than Rs.20,000.

Experience of Online Shopping of the Respondents:

Particulars	No of Respondents	%
Less than a year	11	4.1
2-5 years	124	45.9
6-10 years	88	32.6
Above 10 years	47	17.4
Total	270	100

Interpretation:

From the above table it is clear that out of 270 respondents, 45.9% of the respondents were shopping online for 2-5 years, 32.6% of the respondents were shopping online for 6-10 years, 17.4% of the respondents were shopping online for above 10 years, and the remaining 4.1% of the respondents were shopping online for less than a years. It can be concluded that most of the respondents were experiencing online shopping from 2-5 years.

Preference of Online Shopping Websites of the Respondents:

Particulars	No of Respondents	%
Amazon	77	28.5
Flipkart	79	29.3
Snapdeal	64	23.7
E-bay	50	18.5
Total	270	100

Interpretation:

From the above table it is clear that out of 270 respondents, 50.0% of the respondents spent for online shopping between rs.1001-rs.2000, 21.5% of the respondents spent for online shopping between rs.2001-rs.3000, 15.9% of the respondents spent for online shopping were above rs.3000, and the remaining 12.6% of the respondents spent for online shopping were below rs.1000. It can be concluded that most of the respondents spent for online shopping between rs.1001- rs.2000.

Factors Influencing to Purchase through Online Shopping:

Ranking Based on Kendall's Correlation:

Factors		Wide Range of Products	Free Door Delivery	Low Cost	Discounts and Offers	Quality of Products	24*7 Shopping Facility
Wide range of products	Correlation Coefficient	1	-.165**	-.187**	-.227**	-.131*	-0.079
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	0.002	0	0	0.01	0.14
	N	270	270	270	270	270	270
Free door delivery	Correlation Coefficient	-.165**	1	-.107*	-.202**	-.202**	-0.071
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.002	.	0.038	0	0	0.2
	N	270	270	270	270	270	270
Low cost	Correlation Coefficient	-.187**	-.107*	1	-.214**	-.119*	-.204**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0.038	.	0	0.017	0
	N	270	270	270	270	270	270
Discounts and offers	Correlation Coefficient	-.227**	-.202**	-.214**	1	-.145**	-0.055

	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	.	0.004	0.301
	N	270	270	270	270	270	270
Quality of products	Correlation Coefficient	-.131*	-.202**	-.119*	-.145**	1	-.210**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.01	0	0.017	0.004	.	0
	N	270	270	270	270	270	270
24*7 shopping facility	Correlation Coefficient	-0.079	-0.071	-.204**	-0.055	-.210**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.14	0.2	0	0.301	0	.
	N	270	270	270	270	270	270
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)							
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)							

Interpretation: From the above table it is clear that the Kendall's Coefficient of Concordance used for the study was based on Kendall's correlation factors are negative and with that factor are not correlated with each other.

Descriptive Statistics for Level of Awareness towards Online Shopping Sites:

Shopping Sites	N	Mean Score	Std. Deviation
Flipkart	270	2.28	0.832
Amazon	270	1.49	0.557
Snap deal	270	1.51	0.62
Jabong	270	1.5	0.789
Myntra	270	1.91	0.748
Local banya	270	2.36	0.641
Homeshop18	270	2.56	0.653
Infibeam	270	2.51	0.655
Shopclues	270	2.34	0.617
Firstery	270	2.44	0.738
eBay	270	2.05	0.666
Paytm	270	2.27	0.648
Valid N (list wise)	270		

Interpretation:

From the above table it is clear that the descriptive statistics on level of awareness towards various websites were the above mid mean value (2.0) shows that the sites have high awareness and the websites which has highest awareness in the market is Flipkart as the mean value is greater than other websites at 2.28 as per analysis

Demographic Variables and Experience of Online Shopping:

Demographic Variables	Chi-Square	P Values	Significant / Not Significant
Gender	39.002	0.000	S
Age	1.364	0.000	S
Marital status	9.997	0.019	S
Place	33.357	0.000	S
Educational qualification	1.004	0.000	S
Occupation	16.487	0.170	NS
Monthly income	1.162	0.000	S

S - Significant (P value = 0.05)

Interpretation:

The above table shows that there is a significant association between experience of online shopping and demographic variables like gender, age, marital status, place, educational qualification, and monthly income are less than 0.05. Hence null hypothesis is rejected. There is no significant association between experience of online shopping and demographic variables of occupation as the value is greater than 0.05.

Findings:

Percentage Analysis:

- Male respondents prefer to shop online than female.
- Unmarried respondents prefer to shop online than married.
- Rural area respondents prefer to shop online than urban.
- Most of the respondents prefer to shop online were under the age group of 20-40 years.
- Maximum of the respondents prefer to shop online were graduates.

- Most of the respondents were going for Private Jobs prefer to shop online.
- Maximum of the respondents monthly income were more than Rs.60, 000.
- Most of the respondents were family members who insisted to purchase through online shopping.
- Maximum of the respondents were experiencing online shopping from 2-5 years.
- Most of the respondents were using online shopping for once in 3 months.
- Maximum of the respondents purchased through online were during heavy discount period.
- Most of the respondents spent for online shopping between rs.1001- rs.2000.
- Maximum of the respondents spent for online shopping between rs.1001- rs.2000.
- Free door delivery is the factor that influence most to purchase through online.

Suggestions:

- With so many devices and so many different screen sizes the companies need a design that will look great across all platforms. While their design may look wonderful on a large computer screen, that same design might be clunky and hard to use on a cell phone screen. A responsive design will be beautiful and easy to use on all platforms.
- The companies can give customers a perfect bundles that experts pick out is something that customers really enjoy. It gives them the perfect idea of what to buy. They also feel like they are saving time by having everything they want already packaged together.

Conclusion:

The main objective of the study is to know why customers delay or hesitate to make decision for shopping online and to determine the reasons and suggestions for the problems faced by the customers and the conclusion is that based on the customers perception towards service provided by the companies Flipkart has the highest priority to the service provided and the priority can be given by the customers to purchase their products in this website.

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